

How Increase of Bilirubin in Blood Impacts Cooking Likeness?

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ABSTRACT

Bilirubin is yellow-brownish pigment formed by breaking of dead red blood cells. And its normal value is 200-250 mg in adults. But if it is accumulate in blood flow, then it lead to neurological disorder. And for the checking impact of bilirubin on cooking likeness, and for this purpose 15 males and 65 females were participated. And their urine test is performed according to instructor. And by statistical analysis it is resulted that males who like have more bilirubin in their urine. And thus have more chances of disease.

Keywords: Bilirubin; Neurological; Pigment; Cooking.

INTRODUCTION

When red blood cell breaks down a yellow-brownish material is produce called as bilirubin. This pigment is present in liver and excreted out through digestion. And it also indicate that bilirubin is present in all bodies, because it is produce when red blood cell dying. Its large concentration can lead to jaundice, and skin color change to yellow.

And thus it may cause liver disease. Its concentration is effected by age and other health issues. Babies which have bilirubin more than 20-25 mg in per deciliter lead to cause nervous breakdown. And that's why bilirubin test is performed.

Before test for the bilirubin, you must avoid steroid, birth controlling pills, diuretics, because they change the color of urine but also disturbed it. And check your urine according to your lecturer, and carefully follow their instructions.

Cooking is a universal type of mechanism to transform raw food articles into eatables with more desirable products. It is basic need for survival on this planet like water, oxygen, carbon. And it change from time to time according to the human requirements. And it start from cooking on wood fire to roasting, steaming, frying and heating.

The shortcoming of this study is to check the impact of bilirubin on the cooking likeness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 80 candidates participated. Out of which 65 are females and 15 were males. And their age were between 19 to 23. A questionnaire was prepared that either bilirubin disturbance is influenced by cooking likeness. And for this purpose urine test is performed.

Measurement of bilirubin in urine test

For urine test take two or three specimen of urine, because for the first time urine is concentrated. Take polythene bag in which you urinate. And firstly wash your hands, then in toilet urinate into bag. And then marked it, and take this bag to your instructor for further proceeding.

Study Design

In this question-based study, influence of cooking favorite on bilirubin disturbance. And for this purpose, 80 subjects were participated, and their urine test is check.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis were performed by MS Word. And the impact of bilirubin on cooking favorite is determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Bilirubin is a pigment found in liver and formed by breakdown of red blood cells. It is dangerous when it is accumulated in blood flow. And for this we perform urine test. In 80 subjects to check out its relation with cooking likeness. And the % of subjects who like cooking. In males have 53%. In females have 20%. And thus it is resulted that those males who like cooking have more bilirubin in their urine. Bilirubin test is performed. Before test for the bilirubin, you must avoid steroid, birth controlling pills, diuretics, because they change the color of urine but also disturbed it. In this question based study, influence of cooking favorite on bilirubin disturbance. And for this purpose, 80 subjects were participated, and their urine test is check.

Gender	Cooking favorite		Not - Cooking favorite	
	Bilirubin in urine - present	Bilirubin in urine - absent	Bilirubin in urine - present	Bilirubin in urine - absent
Male	53.3 %	33.3%	6.66%	6.66%
Female	20%	7.6%	26.1%	46.1%

CONCLUSION

It is concluded from this study that the males who like cooking had more chances of bilirubin in their urine.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

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